

Experimental Investigation of Anisotropic Laminate Structural Behavior

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ABSTRACT

Comparisons of experimental stiffnesses and strengths with the theoretical predictions based on lamination theory and four failure criteria are presented for four graphite/epoxy anisotropic laminates under tension, compression and shear loads. The comparison have indicated that the stiffness and strength properties of anisotropic laminate can be predicted if the layer properties are accurately known.

Also, to demonstrate the interaction between bending and twist induced in tailored wing, three kinds of honeycomb sandwich beams were designed and fabricated. Each beam was supported as a cantilever and loaded to measure the deflection modes. Then the test results were compared with linear finite-element-method predictions to determine how closely the method can predict this behavior. The result have indicated that the coupled bending/twist behavior can be closely predicted by the conventional finite-element-method provided the limit of the laminate linear behavior are not significantly exceeded.

INTRODUCTION

The potential for achieving weight and cost saving of aircraft component through the use of advanced composite materials has been well established by the current applications. There is also a potential for exploiting the unique directional properties of composite to: (1) achieve aeroelastic tailoring of wings for flight performance optimization beyond the practical limits of metal design; (2) protect from flutter and divergence efficiently; and (3) maintain surface lift effectiveness, all at significantly lower weight than in metal(1, 2).

For the structural design of tailored wing which makes the most of this unique directional properties of composite, the use of an optimization computer program (Analysis Tool) is mandatory in order to achieve a minimum weight structure while taking account of both strength and aeroelastic requirements (3, 4, 5, 6). Fuji is progressing with the development of the optimization computer program. In parallel with the programming, the following experimental investigations were conducted to verify the theoretical foundation:

- Laminate Property Tests to confirm Lamination Theory for Stiffness and Failure Criteria for Strength of anisotropic laminates
- Beam Tests to validate Finite-Element-Method Prediction for the interaction between bending and twist of wing type structure

These test results and correlations with analysis (theoretical values) are presented in this paper.

MATERIAL PROPERTY TESTS

The advanced composite material used for this study was TORAYCA P3060 graphite/epoxy. The material property of layer necessary to calculate the laminate stiffness and strength was determined from standard coupon tests. Longitudinal and transverse properties were obtained from tests of unidirectional laminates, and shear characteristics from tests of the ± 45 deg laminate (5 longitudinal tension, 16 transverse tension, 10 longitudinal compression, 10 transverse compression and 5 shear).

These test-based layer properties were summarized in Table 1. The shear modulus is nonlinear with load (FIG. 1). G_{LT} shown in Table 1 is the initial shear modulus. The mean values of the tests and the nonlinear stress-strain curve were used in subsequent calculation of anisotropic laminate stiffness and strength properties.

LAMINATE PROPERTY TESTS

Coupon Design

The anisotropic laminate property test was performed twice. Coupon specimens used in the first test gave effectual results for confirmation of lamination theory for stiffness and failure criteria for tension strength. However, there was much room for further improvement in the geometry of coupons used in compression and shear strength tests.

The second test was conducted with the improved coupon specimens. The thickness of compression test specimens was doubled to protect from buckling, and the size of shear test specimens was about twice the first ones to be wide enough to ensure a uniform shear stress field. The geometry and ply orientation of coupon specimens are shown in FIG. 2 for the first test specimens (24 tension, 48 compression, 12 shear) and in FIG. 3 for the second test specimens (24 compression, 12 shear). Four kinds of ply orientation were designed as follows :

	<u>1st TEST & 2nd SHEAR TEST (8-ply)</u>	<u>2nd COMPRESSION TEST (16-ply)</u>
Laminate A	$(\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_2$ s	$(\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ_2/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ_2)$ s
Laminate B	$(\pm 15^\circ/\pm 60^\circ)$ s	$(\pm 15^\circ/\pm 60^\circ/\pm 15^\circ/\pm 60^\circ)$ s
Laminate C	$(30^\circ_3/0^\circ)$ s	$(30^\circ_3/0^\circ/30^\circ_3/0^\circ)$ s
Laminate D	$(15^\circ/\pm 55^\circ/90^\circ)$ s	$(15^\circ/\pm 55^\circ/90^\circ/15^\circ/\pm 55^\circ/90^\circ)$ s

The laminates from which these coupons were made were laid up and stacked using conventional hand layup technique to control fiber orientation and stacking sequence. The laminates were autoclave-cured for 2 hours at 450K (350°F) under 586kPa (6kgf/cm²). The specimens were cut from panels using a band saw. The edge of the specimens were then finished using a fraise to correct edge defects induced by sawing.

Testing and Instrumentation

Test coupons were instrumented with two rosette gages (back-to-back) to measure longitudinal, transverse and shear strains. Each coupon was loaded up to failure by a universal testing machine of the constant rate-of-crosshead-motion type. The load/strain history was accumulated in a cassette data recorder during the tests and plotted on X-Y chart using the electronic data processing system after the tests. A supporting jig presented in (7) was used in compression tests to protect from buckling (FIG. 4).

Test Results and Correlation with Theory

Test results were compared with the theoretical values analyzed in advance. The compliance coefficients, a_{ij} (see FIG. 5), were used in correlation of the laminate stiffness property. The stiffness of anisotropic laminates tested in this study were analyzed using the lamination theory (8). The comparisons of experimental and theoretical compliance coefficients are shown in FIGS. 6(a) through 6(d). It can be seen from these figures that the agreement of both coefficients is good and therefore, the stiffness of anisotropic laminates is adequately determined using the lamination theory.

The experimentally determined strengths were compared with the theoretical predictions using four failure criteria; Tsai-Wu criterion, Hoffman criterion, Maximum strain theory and Maximum stress theory (8, 9, 10). From the comparison following remarks are made:

- (1) The predicted strengths gave relatively good agreements with the test strengths for tension and shear (FIG. 7 and FIG. 8). However, the predicted compression strength could not be confirmed in the agreement with the experimental value as the test data scattered (FIG. 9).
- (2) The first ply failure stress lower than the maximum failure stress in theoretical prediction (e.g. FIG. 10) is close to the test strength (compare FIG 11(a) first ply failure and FIG. 11(b) maximum failure stress). The maximum failure stress falls in a overestimation at times. This difference between the first ply failure stress and the maximum failure stress was noted in tension strength prediction. Both of the failure stresses coincided with each other in compression and shear strength prediction.
- (3) Among the four failure criteria, Tsai-Wu and Hoffman criteria seem to give relatively adequate predictions to the test strength, while the maximum strain and stress theories yield higher failure stresses than the former criteria, and in some cases exceed the test strength.
- (4) It makes a marked difference to the failure stress whether the prediction takes account of the nonlinearity in shear stress-strain characteristics or not (FIG. 12). The nonlinear prediction gives closer failure stresses to the test strength.

BEAM ANALYSIS AND TESTS

Beam Design and Analysis

The purpose of the beam tests was to observe how the axial stress-shear stress coupling of anisotropic laminate covers translates to the displacement-twist behavior of a wing structure, and to determine how closely conventional engineering analysis method can predict this behavior.

Three kinds of honeycomb sandwich panels were designed and fabricated for this study. Two panels of them have the same geometry but the different ply orientation of covers, one is 0° (hereafter referred to as Beam A) and one is 30° (Beam B). The beam configuration is shown in FIG. 13. The uniform laminate covers are separated by honeycomb core. The beam size is 100 mm width x 1,000 mm length x 6.4 mm thickness. The third beam (Beam C), 300 mm x 1,800 mm x 25.4 mm, consists of six bay-different layup anisotropic laminate covers. The configuration and ply orientations are shown in FIG. 14.

The analysis of the displacement-twist behavior of these beams was performed using a finite-element displacement method computer program MASTRAN. The finite-element analyses are based on linear theory, both in treatment of geometry and material properties. The material properties used in the analyses are the laminate stiffness properties calculated from the mean values and the initial shear modulus of the test-based layer properties in Table 1.

Test Results and Correlation with Analysis

Each beam was supported as a cantilever and loaded to measure the bending-twist coupled mode.

Test results of Beams A and B, in the form of tip displacement and twist, were plotted in comparison with the analysis values. One plot of tip shear loading case is shown in FIG. 15. The displacement and twist agree well with analysis. For the tip shear test, the maximum load of 23 N (2.3 kgf) was applied to Beam B. This load level corresponds to approximately 110 percent of the limit design allowables.

Test results of Beam C, in the form of centerline displacement and twist, were plotted as a function of span. One plot is shown in FIG. 16 for tip shear case. Also in this case, there is a good agreement of the test results and analysis.

The linearity of the beam tip displacement and twist with increasing load has also been investigated. The test results, FIG. 15 for Beams A and B, indicated no marked nonlinearity, and also no permanent deformation after unloading.

CONCLUSIONS

The stiffness of anisotropic laminates is adequately predicted using lamination theory if the layer properties of the composite material are reliably known, irrespective of loading (tension, compression or shear).

The strength is only just enough estimated using failure criteria with care to : (1) the maximum failure stress falls in a overestimation of tension strength attimes, (2) Tsai-Wu and Hoffman criteria give relatively adequate predictions, while the maximum strain and stress theories yield higher strengths, (3) the nonlinearity in shear stress-strain characteristics need to be taken account of.

Linear finite-element-method analysis was found to be sufficient to predict the bending/twist interaction for the practical stress levels in design.

This study has shown that only careful analysis using known layer properties can give adequate predictions for the stiffness, strength and coupled displacement-twist behavior of wing type structure employing anisotropic laminates.

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Table 1. TORAYCA P3060 graphite/epoxy material properties

Property		Test Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Coeff. of Variation (%)
STRENGTH	Longitudinal Tension F_L	1568MPa	186MPa	11.9
	Transverse Tension F_T	57	8.5	14.9
	Longitudinal Compression F_L'	1341	84	6.3
	Transverse Compression F_T'	212	22	10.3
	In-Plane Shear F_{LT}	80	1.0	1.3
MODULI	Longitudinal Tension E_L	153GPa	0.93GPa	0.6
	Transverse Tension E_T	11	0.20	1.8
	Longitudinal Compression E_L'	131	4.7	3.6
	Transverse Compression E_T'	10	0.11	1.1
	In-Plane Shear G_{LT}	5.5	0.18	3.3
POISSON'S RATIOS	Major Poisson's Ratio Tension	0.31	0.017	5.5
	Compression	0.35	0.024	6.8
	Minor Poisson's Ratio Tension	0.020	0.0036	18.0
	Compression	0.024	0.00075	3.1

FIG.1 Layer shear stress-strain curve

(a) Tension Specimen

(b) Compression Specimen

	Ply Orientation	
Laminate A	($\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ$) _s	8 PLY
Laminate B	($\pm 15^\circ/\pm 60^\circ$) _s	8 PLY
Laminate C	($30^\circ/0^\circ$) _s	8 PLY
Laminate D	($15^\circ/\pm 5^\circ/90^\circ$) _s	8 PLY

* Dimensions in mm

(c) Shear Specimen

FIG.2 First laminate property test specimens

(a) Compression Specimen

(b) Shear Specimen

FIG.4 Support jig in compression test

FIG.3 Second laminate property test specimens

FIG.5 Compliance coefficients, a_{ij}

FIG.6 Comparison of compliance coefficients

FIG. 7 Comparison of tension strength

FIG. 8 Comparison of shear strength

FIG. 9 Comparison of compression strength

FIG. 10 Tension strength analysis

FIG. 11 Comparison of theoretical predictions for tension strength

FIG.12 Nonlinearity effect on theoretical strength

FIG.13 Configuration of beams A and B

FIG.16 Comparison of analysis and test deformations (beam C)

FIG.14 Configuration of beam C

FIG.15 Comparison of analysis and test deformations (beams A and B)